

ACCELERATED LIFETIME AND RELIABILITY TESTING OF LARGE-DEFLECTION PIEZOELECTRIC MICROSYSTEMS

R.Q. Rudy¹, L.M. Sanchez¹, M. Tellers^{1,2}, and R.G. Polcawich¹

¹US Army Research Laboratory, Adelphi, MD, USA

²University of Maryland, College Park, MD, USA

ABSTRACT

This paper reports, for the first time, accelerated lifetime testing and reliability of large displacement piezoelectric micro-electromechanical systems (MEMS) over trillions of cycles. Electrical, mechanical, and piezoelectric properties of cantilevers have been monitored over time and the surface topology has been observed through scanning electron microscopy.

KEYWORDS

Piezoelectric, lifetime, MEMS, reliability.

INTRODUCTION

As piezoelectric MEMS devices become more widespread, there is a need to develop a deeper understanding of the failure mechanisms and lifetime performance trends, however, extensive lifetime testing research has not yet been reported in the literature. Lead zirconate titanate (PZT) is among the most attractive materials for actuator applications due to its large transverse piezoelectric coefficient, e_{31f} , and existing large-scale deposition and patterning processes. Polcawich et al. [1] reported on piezoelectric coefficients, measured through the direct effect, over 1 billion cycles at fields of 120–200 kV/cm. Mazzalai et al. [2] recently reported cycling of PZT up to 1 billion cycles using the converse piezoelectric effect; however this was performed with a full wafer thickness beneath the thin-film PZT, resulting in low deflections. For many actuator applications, such as small-scale robotics [3] or RF switches [4], large deflections within the system provide a new paradigm for experimentation. The present work examines the reliability and failure mechanisms in large deflection PZT MEMS.

Accelerated lifetime testing was performed by exciting unimorph piezoelectric cantilevers at mechanical resonance. Mechanical resonance excitation allows for amplified deflections due to the mechanical quality factor enhancement in the system. Electrical, mechanical and piezoelectric properties were monitored throughout the test to determine the effects of large displacement in these MEMS structures. At various points throughout testing the cantilever structures were imaged using scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and electrical properties (capacitance, dielectric loss, polarization hysteresis) were recorded. Quasi-static and resonance deflections were measured through laser Doppler vibrometry (LDV) using a Polytec OFV-5000. Long duration testing revealed that fracture occurred at high cycle counts suggesting that fatigue may be present in these tests.

Figure 1: SEM micrograph of tested cantilever after 2 trillion cycles, with various defects present.

METHODS

The cantilevers examined were fabricated according to the process outlined in [4]. The Pt/PZT/Pt actuator stack is deposited on a multi-layer silicon oxide/nitride stack to reduce residual stress gradient induced deformation that prevents proper characterization using LDV. The PZT has a Zr/Ti ratio of 52/48 and is highly textured in the 001 direction with a Lotgering of at least 0.95. The Pt/PZT/Pt stack is patterned using Ar ion milling. The silicon oxide/nitride stack is patterned using a reactive ion etch. A Ti/Pt adhesion layer is evaporated followed by a gold layer for wirebonding. Once complete the devices are released by etching the underlying silicon using an isotropic XeF₂ etch.

The released devices were placed in a dual inline package and wirebonded. Initial SEM and electrical characterization was performed and the devices were actuated with a sinusoidal input at 1 V_{rms} and the frequency was swept until a maximum was observed in the deflection response of the second cantilever (~300 kHz). The cantilever array was then actuated at this optimal frequency with a sinusoid at varying voltages. The sinusoid was stopped on regular intervals to perform intermediate characterization using SEM and electrical measurement. A scanning electron microscopy image of the cantilever array after 2 trillion cycles is shown in Figure 1, above.

Figure 2: Scanning electron microscopy over a number of cycles. The red arrow at 10^9 cycles highlights the first defects, and the red box at 10^{11} cycles shows the formation of a crack at a high stress point.

Figure 3: Polarization ($\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$) as a function of electric field (kV/cm) over cycles show increased imprint, evident from the shift of the loop center in the negative x -direction, and increased loop width.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

After performing initial tests, cycle counts of 10^8 , 10^9 , 10^{10} , and 10^{11} were selected to monitor defects and failure. Figure 2 shows the three shortest cantilevers in the array at these stages in the lifetime cycling test. The actuation signal was a 0-6 V (electric field of 0-60 kV/cm) sinusoid with frequency equal to the fundamental resonance frequency of the second cantilever. In initial tests it was observed that this resonance frequency shifts slightly over time, either from changes in mass or stiffness. As the resonance frequency changes, the actuation frequency is adjusted to maintain the same level of quality factor amplification of the deflection. This was checked at each step with variations of approximately 300 Hz. This small change ($\sim 1\%$) has limited effect on amplitude because of the relative small quality factors observed (~ 30 -50). Figure 2 contains SEM micrographs of the cantilevers at each cycle count. Noticeable defects appear in these time-stepped images at 10^9 cycles, and a crack at the base of the cantilever appears at 10^{11} cycles. SEM of the device from previous intervals shows no evidence of crack propagation, which suggests failure occurred in the material after more than 10^{10} cycles.

Figure 3 plots the polarization ($\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$) vs. electric field (kV/cm) hysteresis curves over cycles. The initial hysteresis loop is narrower and the loop widens over time. Wider loops imply that there is more loss due to switching domains in the PZT. The loops also shift in the negative x -

direction indicating imprint in the PZT film. Imprint in piezoelectric materials arises from a preferable domain orientation. The DC bias in the sinusoidal signal poles the PZT during actuation leading to increased imprint. Interestingly, there is no significant change in maximum polarization as a function of cycle time.

Figure 1 is a SEM image of an actuated cantilever array after 2 trillion cycles. Here, defects occur on the second cantilever, but also the seventh cantilever. Defects in the first cantilever are concentrated at the tip of the cantilever. However in the seventh cantilever, defects are located at the tip and midway along the beam seemingly corresponding to the 2nd resonance mode. Figure 4a shows the measured resonance deflection of both cantilevers using LDV, and Figure 4b shows the modeled resonance deflection of the cantilevers using a harmonic analysis in ANSYS R14.5.

It is clear that the resonance amplification is significantly contributing to defect accumulation, and it was hypothesized that the defects were frictional polymers accumulated from the ambient environment similar to those observed on electrical relays operated in ambient conditions [5]. To test this, a cantilever set was excited on a probe station with nitrogen overpressure for 100 billion cycles. After this cycling, there were no notable defects like those seen in Figure 1 or 2, supporting the hypothesis that the high velocity and large displacement of the cantilevers at resonance causes potential deposition of polymers from the ambient environment.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4: The first and second resonant mode (a) measured using LDV, and (b) modeled in ANSYS R14.5. The defects occur at the points of peak vibration amplitude

CONCLUSION

This set of high cycle reliability in large displacement piezoelectric MEMS provides a new area to explore. The cycling of cantilevers over 2 trillion cycles at fields of $\sim 60\text{kV/cm}$ is encouraging for applying piezoelectric materials to long life-scale applications, especially considering the large deflections that occur. The existence of frictional polymers deposited on these active devices is important to consider for devices open to the atmosphere, especially where velocities and displacements can be large.

In future tests it would be interesting to examine the device response under various actuation amplitudes to examine the relationship between deflection amplitude and cycles to failure. Because failure occurred due to cracks at

the base of the cantilever and not a fundamental material failure, improving device design to eliminate stress concentrations should also lead to higher cycle counts and longer lifetimes. This is also important for device designers because components which do not fail on initial testing, could fail due to cycling if not properly designed. If other electrode materials can be introduced, such as iridium oxide, which should help mitigate depoling effects from bipolar cycling, it would be interesting to compare lifetimes under bipolar actuation beyond the coercive field.

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CONTACT

*R.Q. Rudy, tel:+1-301-394-2324;
ryan.q.rudy.civ@mail.mil